

MARKETING STRATEGY AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the marketing strategy and the mechanisms of its implementation in the higher education system of Uzbekistan, it analyzes the main types of marketing strategies used in the field of higher education and their main directions, the essence of the market of educational services and educational services is highlighted. specific features of services are based, marketing strategy in the higher education system and mechanisms of its implementation are researched, systematic work and main indicators implemented in the higher education system are analyzed, supply and demand for highly educated personnel is analyzed*

Keywords: *higher education, marketing in the higher education system, education system, marketing, strategy, marketing strategy, system, mechanism, mechanism of strategies, higher education. human resources, higher education system, market of educational services, mechanisms of implementation of marketing strategy, higher education sector, types of marketing strategy, higher education institutions, "portfolio of orders", "students and practice department", state education standards, training of qualified personnel, international standards, development concept, competition in education, higher education institutions, ranking of universities, demand and supply in higher education.*

Introduction

The following strategic goals of the development of the higher education system are defined in the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019:

- increase the quality of highly qualified personnel training for socio-economically stable development;
- modernization of the country;
- training of highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking personnel who can make independent decisions based on international standards;
- development of human capital based on labor market requirements;
- to increase the level of coverage with higher education, to create the necessary conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and formation as a spiritually mature person;
- forming a healthy competitive environment in the industry, increasing its attractiveness, ensuring global competitiveness.

These strategic goals are directly related to marketing strategies in the higher education system. But in practice, the possibilities of using marketing strategies in the implementation of these strategic goals are very limited.

Research methodology

The limited opportunities for using marketing strategies are explained by the following problems and shortcomings in the higher education system:

1. The powers of the state higher education institutions operating in the republic in the field of academic and organizational management are insufficient.

2. Taking into account the needs of young people to obtain higher education, a system has not been created that envisages helping them to effectively prepare for admission, as well as more effectively organizing career guidance and selection work.

3. One of today's demands is to simplify the approval of the admission parameters for the admission of students to state higher education institutions. The financial independence of higher education institutions is limited as a result of the fact that higher education institutions do not set admission parameters, especially the parameters of admission on the basis of a fee-contract, and do not take into account the cost of each student. According to the current procedure, the order of admission of students to state higher education institutions is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the parameters of admission of students based on the state grant are determined by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

4. The formation of the educational process based on international experiences has not been systematically implemented. In the conditions of academic independence and the transition to international standards, there is no perfect and fast-moving mechanism for identifying, studying and effectively introducing advanced, current international innovations and experiences in the educational and methodological direction into the educational practice of higher education institutions.

5. Due to the fact that enterprises and organizations have not created enough conditions for the organization of student internships, there are problems in the quality organization of internships.

6. In order to increase the level of education coverage of young people in the republic and to create a healthy competitive environment in the field of higher education, a number of problems remain regarding the establishment of non-state higher education institutions in the regions of our republic.

7. There is a need to create a single electronic database of information resource centers of higher education institutions and to improve the system of rapid delivery of educational literature to users.

8. The indicator of scientific potential in higher education institutions of the republic (38 percent) remains low.

9. The international recognition of the republic's higher education institutions and their place in the ranking of world universities remains low.

10. The indicator of publication activity of professors and teachers working in higher education institutions of the republic remains at a low level. The number of articles published in scientific journals indexed in the internationally recognized scientific and technical databases such as "Scopus", "Web of Science" is low compared to the number of academic staff in the republic, and this prevents higher education institutions from entering international ratings.

11. In the process of equipping scientific research laboratories of higher educational institutions with modern equipment and equipment mainly produced abroad, a complex procedure is emerging. There are not enough materials (including reagents) and qualified professionals to use them. At the same time, there are currently 39 scientific laboratories in 15 higher education

institutions. However, the equipment of modern scientific laboratories in most higher education institutions in our republic is not up to the required level.

12. A transparent and open mechanism for the recruitment of teaching staff of higher education institutions has not been created.

13. State higher education institutions have a number of restrictions (norms) on spending the funds they have earned and received in the Development Fund. This prevents higher education institutions from earning additional funds and spending them independently.

Nowadays, "Department of Marketing and Student Practice" is established in every state higher education institution. The organizational structure of this department can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 1. Organizational structure of the Department of Marketing and Student Practice

These sections are in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On admission to higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the 2005/2006 academic year" No. - number, "On measures to introduce new principles of management in the system of higher and secondary special education" dated July 11, 2019 PQ-4391 and the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to accelerate marketing in the field of education market formation and personnel training" Decision No. 48 of January 28, 1998 conducts its activities based on the Model Regulation developed on the basis of

Results of the research

The following tasks are assigned to these departments:

creating a complete data bank by assessing the structure of consumers of educational services, determining their geographical location and grouping, diagnosing their potential opportunities, including the ratio of supply and demand for graduates in undergraduate education and master's specialties;

formation of a database based on the study of the needs of enterprises, institutions and organizations for highly educated personnel being trained at a higher educational institution;

introducing the relevant issues related to the improvement of the quality of trained personnel for discussion in the Councils of the higher education institution, establishing cooperation with the relevant departments of the higher education institution in this regard;

training of personnel in a higher educational institution and monitoring of job distribution of graduates based on state grants, systematic analysis and evaluation of employment of graduates;

step-by-step development of market relations in the field of education, assistance in its improvement, formation of a realistic "portfolio of orders" for graduating bachelors and masters based on indicators of demand for young professionals;

directing the activity of the higher education institution to meet the demands and needs of personnel;

taking into account the rapid change of marketing service processes in the higher education system and the interrelationship with the dynamics of the labor market development, in cooperation with potential employers (consumers), to study the need for highly educated young professionals in the branches and sectors of the republic's economy by region;

analyzing the changes in the service market conjuncture and preparing proposals for defining new directions of development;

development of practical proposals for training of highly educated personnel based on the needs of the economic sectors and in accordance with the current and prospective development programs of the regions;

establishment of mutual cooperation and communication with organizations interested in the training of specialist personnel, including studying opinions on the quality and potential of personnel;

participation in the preparation and implementation of draft decisions on personnel training directions and the market of educational services;

developing proposals for ensuring competitive, highly qualified personnel training;

to support the use of young professionals based on the demands and needs of personnel consumers;

discussing the requirements of the customers regarding the quality of personnel in the process of personnel training in the council of the higher education institution;

ensuring mutual cooperation of departments of specialization and personnel orderers;

organization of graduate students' practice in enterprises and organizations where the student will be employed;

constant study of internal and external labor market conditions, formation of proposals for admission parameters based on consumer orders for graduates, organization of the database of the higher education institution on admission, student contingent, employment of graduates;

to ensure that the recommendations and suggestions of consumers and specialist departments regarding the young specialist are taken into account in the assignment of a graduate to a job based on the current situation;

to ensure the signing of contracts related to the organization of students' professional practice and their organization in relevant organizations in the prescribed manner;

to study, analyze the processes of organization of student practice and develop proposals for solving problems;

study of advanced foreign and national experiences on organization of student practice and preparation of proposals for its implementation.

Today, the reforms implemented in higher education require improvement of the content of higher education based on modern requirements, training of mature specialists with professional knowledge, skills and practical skills at the level of requirements of personnel customers.

Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 1, 2008 No. 2961 "On measures to ensure the training of professional personnel required in real sectors and sectors of the economy" (Figure 2.8):

monitoring the demand for graduates of higher educational institutions within the regions of the republic in real branches and sectors of the economy, on a permanent basis;

to provide economic sectors with highly educated personnel, to provide an expert assessment of the demand for personnel in the relevant areas and specialties determined by economic sectors and regions;

setting parameters for admission of students for the coming academic year, setting quotas for admission with grant and contract payment based on real requirements for personnel;

Every year until April 1, the State Commission is assigned the task of submitting reasonable proposals for the admission of students to higher education institutions in relevant fields and specialties.

Figure 2. Scheme of formation of admission parameters of republican higher education institutions

In accordance with this decision, in each academic year, the ministries and agencies in the system of which higher education institutions are operating will form offers for admission quotas in accordance with the prospective needs of higher educated personnel of potential employers, organizations and institutions in each field of education and specialization.

In addition, appropriate measures will be implemented in order to form the composition of educational directions and specializations and admission quotas in accordance with the sectoral and regional needs of the economy, and proposals will be developed for admission parameters for each academic year to the republic's higher education institutions.

Analyses

According to the Program for the comprehensive development of the higher education system in 2017-2021, "determining the quantitative indicators of the training of highly educated

personnel and the composition of educational directions (specializations) in accordance with the priority directions of the development of regions and economic sectors, taking into account the implementation of projects of sectoral and regional programs in 2017-2021 organization of personnel training in new educational areas in educational institutions, re-specialization of existing higher education institutions in the republic's regions and organization of branches of higher education institutions, taking into account the peculiarities and priorities of the development of economic sectors and regions"tasks are defined.

Although marketing strategies have been developed by some higher education institutions, these marketing strategies have not been developed to the level of demand and their effectiveness has not been evaluated.

Conclusions

In short, the limited possibilities of developing marketing strategies, their effective use, and the fact that the tasks set before them by the relevant departments of higher education institutions are not carried out at the required level indicate the need to develop marketing strategies and improve the mechanisms of their implementation in the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

1. It is known that a number of problems and shortcomings remain in the analysis of the higher education system of the Republic. Including:

a) The formation of the educational process based on international experiences has not been systematically implemented. In the conditions of academic independence and the transition to international standards, there is no perfect and fast-moving mechanism for identifying, studying and effectively introducing advanced, current international innovations and experiences in the educational and methodological direction into the educational practice of higher education institutions.

b) Taking into account the needs of young people to obtain higher education, a system has not been created to help them prepare effectively for admission, as well as more effectively organize career guidance and selection work.

c) due to the insufficient competences of the state higher education institutions in the field of academic and organizational management, problems remain in ensuring the quality of education and organizing educational processes on time and at the level of demand.

g) In order to increase the level of inclusion of young people in the republic with higher education and to create a healthy competitive environment in the field of higher education, there are some problems in the establishment of non-state higher education institutions in the regions of our republic.

2. Employersproblems arise in the process of hiring highly educated specialists. The main reason for the emergence of these problems is that young professionals demand a higher salary than the salary offered by the organization, at the same time, there is a need for personnel with sufficient qualifications in the labor market.

3. Vocational orientation of applicants and students needs radical improvement. At the same time, general secondary and secondary special education systems have little influence on the choice of specialty.

4. Currently, there is no system in the country that represents the interests of the parties in terms of close cooperation with higher education institutions.

5. Development of marketing strategies, limited opportunities for effective use of them, failure to fulfill the tasks set before them by relevant departments of higher education institutions show the need to develop marketing strategies and form mechanisms for its implementation in the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

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